

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF STITCHED 3D-WOVEN-COMPOSITES/TITANIUM SINGLE-LAP JOINT

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ABSTRACT

The effect of tow size of sutures, stitch density (SD) and stitching hole diameter (HD) on strength of the 3D-woven composites/titanium single-lap joint is presented in this paper. Specimens with different tow size (24k,48k) and stitch density (SD=0.0313/mm², 'stitched 4*8', SD=0.0208/mm², 'stitched 6*8' and SD=0.0156/mm², 'stitched 8*8') are tested and compared with unstitched joint. The experiment shows that the specimen with 48k suture and stitched 4*8 has the highest strength. Specimens with different stitching hole diameter (HD=2mm, HD=4mm, HD=6mm) was also tested. The experiment shows specimens with HD=2mm and HD=4mm have almost the same strength, and bigger HD leads to lower stiffness. The behaviour of the sutures in the test shows there are two stages of the failure: composite-titanium interface failure and suture failure

1 INTRODUCTION

With the more and more application of the 3D woven composites in airplane, the joint between 3D woven composites and metal material, such as titanium alloy, must be stable and reliable. Riveting and bolting and adhesive bonding are the conventional choices for joining structures. However, rivet or bolt joints need to drill a hole through the 3D woven composites, which will create many microcracks around the hole and break the structure of the yarns. On the other hand, because of the high stress concentration at the ends of the adhesive joints, the adhesive bonded joint is also not reliable.

The stitching joining technique refers to a special process of joining the preforms by sutures in the thickness direction. Typically, composites are stitched together and then integrally formed using RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) or RFI (Resin Film Infusion). Compared to conventional adhesive joints, stitching composites joints have a better ability to withstand out-of-plane loads due to the presence of sutures. The stitched joint area maintains high strength when subjected to out-of-plane peel stress [1] or after impact damage [2], thereby increasing the load carrying capacity and service life of the structure. Though many researches gave opposite result in how stitching influence the in-plane mechanical performance of the laminate [3], Stitching is proofed can strengthen the lap joints [4-6] and T-joints [7-8]. The sutures are found remain intact when the crack starts growing so it can also increase the fatigue life of the joint [9-10]. On the other hand, stitching process is before forming, so the stitching technique does not cause additional damage to the joint.

The main aim of this paper is to find out the failure mechanism of three-dimensional-woven-composites/titanium-alloy single-lap joints. Specimens with different stitching parameters were tested and a microscope connected with an industrial camera was used to record the performance of the joints and the sutures during the test. That performance are used to reveal the failure mechanism of the joint.

2 TEST

2.1 Specimens

The specimens used in this study consisted of two identical titanium-alloy/3D-woven-composite plate that co-cured after stitching as Fig.1 shown.

The dry fiber in the 3-d woven composite material and the titanium alloy plate are first joined together by sutures (since the needle cannot penetrate the titanium alloy plate, some stitching hole will be opened on the titanium alloy plate before stitching so that the sutures can pass the titanium). After stitching, it is integrally solidified by RFM. In order to keep the sample vertical during the test, the blocks are stuck at both ends of the sample.

Figure 1: The specimen used in this study.

Samples are divided into 10 groups. Each group have the same stitching pitch=8mm, composite thickness=5mm, width=24mm and lap length=16.5mm. Each group has certain stitch density($0.0156/\text{mm}^2$ ($s=8\text{mm}$), $0.0208/\text{mm}^2$ ($s=6\text{mm}$), $0.0313/\text{mm}^2$ ($s=4\text{mm}$)), tow size of sutures (24k,48k), titanium thickness(1mm,2mm) and stitching hole diameter(2mm,4mm,6mm). Compare them we can find out how these parameters influence the joint's mechanical properties. A control group whose joint is non-stitched is also tested to show the effect of stitching.

Group Number	Tow size of sutures	Stitch space s(mm)	Stitch density (mm^{-2})	Stitching hole diameter hd(mm)	Titanium thickness t(mm)
1	24k	4	0.0313	2	1
2	48k	4	0.0313	2	1
3	48k	6	0.0208	2	1
4	48k	8	0.0156	2	1
5	48k	8	0.0156	2	2
6	48k	8	0.0156	4	2
7	48k	8	0.0156	6	2
8	No stitching	No stitching	No stitching	No stitching	1

Table 1: Specifications of specimens.

2.2 Test Procedure

All tests in this study were performed at room temperature and humidity. During the test, a

Figure 2: Observation system and experimental setup.

microscope connected with an industrial camera was used to observe damage signs such as microcracks appearing before joint failure. The test machine recorded the test force and the displacement of the upper beam during the test. The deformation of the specimen was recorded by an extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm. In order to observe the failure mode of the specimen with the microscope, the test employed a low loading rate of 0.5 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

3.1 Effect of tow size of sutures

Group 1 (24k 4*8 hd=2 t=1) and Group 2 (48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1) has the same hd, t and stitch density. The test result of them are used to find out how different tow size effect on the single-lap joint. Fig.3 shows the typical load/displacement curve of the two group and the unstitched control group. The average failure load of 24k 4*8 hd=2 t=1 specimens is 6.00kN and that of 48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1 specimens is 7.56kN. The use of 48k tows in suture which can withstand greater tensile and shear loads can increase the load carrying capacity of the joint by 26%.

Another interesting thing should be noticed is when the displacement is over 0.25mm, the slop of both group's load/displacement curve decrease. This phenomenon has also been observed in other specimens' load/displacement curve. The displacement at which the slope changes is similar to the failure displacement that can be sustained by the specimens in unstitched control group (0.25mm). The adhesive between the titanium alloy and the 3D-woven composite fail at 0.25mm and the existence of sutures makes the interface fail at a lower displacement. The failure of the interface leads to the decrease of the overall modulus of the joint.

3.2 Effect of stitch density

Group 2 (48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1), Group 3 (48k 6*8 hd=2 t=1) and Group 4 (48k 8*8 hd=2 t=1) has the same hd and t and stitched by the same sutures. The test result of them are used to find out how the stitch density effect on the single-lap joint. Fig.4 shows the typical load/displacement curve of the

three

Figure 3: Load against displacement curve of 24k 4*8 hd=2 t=1, 48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1 and unstitched control group

Figure 4: Load against displacement curve of 48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1, 48k 6*8 hd=2 t=1, 48k 8*8 hd=2 t=1 and unstitched control group

group and the control group. The average failure load of 48k 4*8 hd=2 t=1 specimens is 7.56kN, that of 48k 6*8 hd=2 t=1 is 5.72kN and of 48k 8*8 hd=2 t=1 is 4.27kN. The average failure load of 6*8 group is 34% higher than that of 8*8 group. The average failure load of 4*8 group is 77% higher than that of 8*8 group. It shows that when the stitching density is low, the effect of strengthening the joint by increasing the stitching density is very obvious.

It is also can be observed that between 2kN and 4kN, the curve of 6*8 is basically coincident with the curve of 8*8. It shows that the stiffness of the specimens after metal-composite interface failure is quite the same.

3.3 Effect of stitching hole diameter

During the manufacturing, bigger stitching holes on the titanium plane makes it easier to stitch and can reduce the manufacturing cost. Group 5 (48k 8*8 hd=2 t=1), Group 6 (48k 8*8 hd=4 t=1) and Group 7 (48k 8*8 hd=6 t=1) has the same stitching density and t and stitched by the same sutures. The test result of them are used to find out how the stitch density effect on the single-lap joint. Fig.5 shows the typical load/displacement curve of the three group and the control group. The average failure load of 48k 8*8 hd=2 t=2 specimens is 10.44kN, that of 48k 8*8 hd=4 t=2 is 10.68kN and of 48k 8*8 hd=6 t=2 is 7.88kN.

The average failure load of hd=4 group and hd=2 group are almost the same, and 35% higher than that of hd=6 group. This reveals that within a certain range, the diameter of the stitching hole has almost no effect on the failure load of the joint, and when the diameter of the stitching hole exceeds a certain level, the failure load of the joint is significantly reduced. On the other hand, it can be clearly seen in Fig. 5 that as the hd increases, the slope of the load/displacement curve decreases. This is because during the RFM process, the gap between the stitching hole and the sutures is filled with the matrix material. After the diameter of the stitching hole becomes larger, the matrix material filled in the gap will also increase. That leads to a decrease in the stiffness of the sutures and finally affecting the overall stiffness of the joint. Therefore, an appropriate amount of matrix also contributes to the shear strength of the sutures while reducing the tensile strength of them, so compare to the result of hd=2, the failure load of the hd=4 group does not show a particularly significant drop.

Figure 5: Load against displacement curve of 48k 8*8 hd=2 t=2, 48k 8*8 hd=4 t=2 and 48k 8*8 hd=6 t=2

3.4 Failure mechanism

In 3.2, the phenomenon that the slope of the load/displacement curve decrease when the displacement of each sample of t=1 is about 0.25 mm has been discussed. To further explain this phenomenon, some test pieces were made and cut at the stitching holes, and the sutures behavior in the test was observed using a microscopic observation device.

Fig. 6 shows one of the cut test pieces, and Fig. 7 is the load/displacement curve of this specimen. In Fig. 6 A, the test has just started and the specimen is intact and no cracks. As can be seen from fig.7, the slope of the load/displacement curve begins to decrease at a displacement of about 0.2 mm. At this time, the failure of the composite-titanium interface causes stress redistribution, and the sutures bear most of the load. A 45° crack was generated in the weft of the 3D woven composite near the stitching hole left above the sutures. When the displacement reaches 0.3 mm, the crack becomes clearly visible, as shown in Fig. 6 B, and the crack continues to expand during loading. As the crack extend to the interface of the sutures and the 3D woven composite, the crack changes direction and extend along the interface. Fig.6 C shows the crack extended to the interface between the sutures and the 3D woven composite. The displacement at this time is about 0.7 mm. Finally, when the load exceeds the failure load of the joint, crack appears on the sutures and the joint fails. Cracks on the sutures of this test piece appeared in the right surface of the titanium plane. By the way, in other test cracks on the sutures were also observed on the shear surface or on the leftmost end of the sutures.

Figure 6: Crack extension during a test

Figure 7: Load against displacement curve of the specimen

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the effect of tow size of sutures, stitch density and stitching hole diameter on strength of the 3D-woven composites/titanium single-lap joint. Specimens were stitched with different tow size and different stitch density were tested in order to find out the influence of these parameter.

Higher stitch density and 48k tow size are known can provide larger joint strength. During the test, the suddenly decrease of the stiffness of the joint shows some failure happened and the crack initial near the sutures shows there was a stress redistribution. The failure of the composite-titanium interface is a reasonable explanation for this phenomenon.

Stitching hole diameter can also affect the strength and stiffness of the joint. The stiffness decrease when the hole becomes bigger. However, due to the matrix material in the stitching hole shares part of the shear stress, the strength of the joint remains at a relatively high level until the stitch hole is too large and the sutures lost its effect.

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